

Continuous version of a square-well potential of variable range and its application in molecular dynamics simulations.

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Abstract

In this work we present a simple mathematical expression for a continuous version of the square-well discontinuous potential of variable range ($\lambda \geq 1.05$). This expression can be useful in theoretical statistical mechanics methods and specially in conventional molecular dynamics simulations. To illustrate the latter point the continuous version of some square-well potentials of variable range were selected and studied with continuous molecular dynamics. Square-well single state thermodynamic and structural properties (vapor, liquid and solid), vapor liquid phase diagrams and surface tensions accurately reproduce available simulation data obtained by Monte Carlo and Discontinuous Molecular Dynamics simulation methods. This expression can be easily implemented in popular simulation packages (GROMACS, NAMD, CHARMM, DL_POLY, EXPResSo, HOOMD, TINKER, ls1 mardyn, etc.) that can be useful to study more complex systems. Besides we also present a continuous version for the square-shoulder potential.

Keywords: Molecular dynamics simulation, continuous square-well potential, Continuous Square-shoulder potential

1 Introduction

In Statistical Mechanics, Hard-Sphere (HS), Square-Well (SW), Square-Shoulder (SS) potentials and some of their combinations (Discrete potentials) have been used as toy models in the context of fluids due to their mathematical simple expressions. Discrete potentials simplify the calculus of terms that appear in the evaluation of Virial Coefficients, Perturbation Theory and Integral Equations Methods [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18]. Although they are simple and discontinuous potentials, they have been used as effective models for real systems, as for example in the modelling of colloids [19, 20, 21, 22] and proteins [23, 24, 25]. The SS potential does not exhibit a vapor-liquid transition however it has a very reach fluid-solid and solid-solid phase diagrams. It has been shown that this potential predicts that particles can self-organize in highly complex, low-symmetry lattices, forming clusters, columns, or lamellae and at high pressures they form compact and high-symmetry structures [26, 27]. A very interesting application has been recently presented by Pattabhiraman et al. [28] using the SS model potential while designing photonic crystals. Besides stripe patterns have been observed for two dimensional SS potentials [29, 30, 31]. In two dimensions SW potentials also exhibits a variety of different phases: vapor, liquid, hexatic and triangular solid and a non compact solid with square-lattice symmetry [32].

Simulation studies for discrete potentials have been mostly performed with Monte Carlo (MC) techniques [33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54]. Due to their discontinuities this kind of potentials has not been treated by conventional molecular dynamics simulation (MD) that is a very important technique that has been applied to many continuous potentials and successfully incorporated in more general popular simulation packages (GROMACS [55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61], CHARMM [62], DL_POLY [63], EXPResSo [64], IMD [65], LAMMPS [66], ls1 mardyn [67], NAMD [68], TINKER [69], HOOMD [70, 71], etc.) to study a great variety of complex sys-

tems. Besides MD simulation has the advantage over the Monte Carlo method that one can obtain the transport properties of a given potential.

The Discontinuous Molecular Dynamics (DMD)[32, 44, 72, 73, 74, 75] is an alternative simulation method that avoids solving the Newton equations for model potentials with discontinuous forces. Instead they solve collisions among particles while obeying the conservation of energy and momentum of the system. However, DMD method has not been implemented until recently to standard simulation packages for event-driven molecular dynamics [76] and its use has been mostly limited to homemade simulation programs in the context of particular problems.

A way of avoiding the difficulties of treating hard-core potentials with MD simulations is the Constant Force Approach method (CFA) proposed by Orea et al. [77]. This method consists in replacing the hard-core discontinuity by a very steep linear function whose derivative is a constant. The extension to a potential with more than one discontinuities has been recently done by Padilla and Benavides [78] and results for discrete potentials are promising.

Another way of handling the discontinuity of the hard-sphere potential (HS) in many MD simulations has been done replacing it by continuous functions of the form $1/r^n$, with n being an integer whose value is around 60. An improved continuous version of a HS potential was developed by Jover et al. [52]. They proposed a continuous version of the HS potential, the so called pseudo hard-sphere potential, that is a cutted and shifted version of a Mie potential with exponents (50-49). They have been able to accurately reproduce structural and thermodynamics properties when compared with available simulation data for the original HS system. Besides, the pseudo hard sphere potential has been successfully applied to study the liquid-solid coexistence using MD direct coexistence method [79].

Other discontinuous potentials that have been expressed as continuous functions to be studied by MD simulations are the square shoulder [80, 81], the discrete potential made of a square shoulder plus a square-well potentials (SS+SW) by Franzese [82] and the smooth version of the Jagla potential, the Fermi-Jagla potential [83].

In this work, we will provide an analytic continuous expression for a SW potential of variable range that can be used in conventional MD simulations. We describe the details of this potential in Section I. MD simulation details are given in Section II. Results of thermodynamic and structural properties and vapor liquid phase diagrams for SW potentials of ranges $\lambda = 1.25, 1.5,$ and 2.0 are presented in Section III and compared with available SW simulation data. As a corollary we present a continuous version of the SS potential. Finally, in Section IV we give the main conclusions of this study.

2 Continuous square well potential

The simplest model of a fluid whose particles interact with repulsive and attractive forces is the square-well potential, U_{SW} , that in reduced units can be expressed as:

$$u_{SW}(x) = \begin{cases} \infty & 0 < x \leq 1, \\ -1 & 1 < x \leq \lambda, \\ 0 & \lambda < x, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $u_{SW}(x) = U_{SW}(x)/\epsilon$, ϵ the depth of the SW potential, $x = r/\sigma$ is the reduced interparticle distance, σ is the molecular diameter, and λ the SW potential range.

A continuous version of the reduced square-well potential, hereafter referred as Continuous Square Well (CSW), takes the form:

$$u_{CSW}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{1}{x} \right)^n + \frac{1 - e^{-m(x-1)(x-\lambda)}}{1 + e^{-m(x-1)(x-\lambda)}} - 1 \right), \quad (2)$$

where n and m are free parameters characterizing the softness of the repulsive and attractive parts of the potential, respectively. CSW potential is continuous over all domain. By construction this potential is zero in $x = 1$, it has only one minimum (-1) in approximately $x = (\lambda + 1)/2$. Moreover, the reduced CSW force, $f_{CSW} = F_{CSW}\sigma/\epsilon$, is also continuous as is required in traditional MD simulations.

$$f_{CSW}(x) = -\frac{n}{2} \left(\frac{1}{x} \right)^{n+1} + \frac{m(2x - \lambda - 1)e^{-m(x-1)(x-\lambda)}}{(1 + e^{-m(x-1)(x-\lambda)})^2}. \quad (3)$$

For all cases considered in this work the exponents were selected $n = 2500$ and $m = 20000$ (See Figure 1). These such big exponents values reproduce the expected natural form of a continuous version of the potential and force simultaneously for square-well potentials of ranges $\lambda \geq 1.05$. Besides for these selected values the potential tends to zero at a slightly greater distance than the SW range. The same expression, Eq. (2), can still be used for smaller ranges ($1 < \lambda < 1.05$) but using higher values for n and m . The continuous hard sphere case is only recovered in the limit when $\lambda \rightarrow 1$ and $m \rightarrow \infty$.

3 Simulation details

We performed molecular dynamics simulations by using the GROMACS package version 5.1. We have chosen argon simulations with particle diameter $\sigma = 0.3405$ nm., energy minimum $\epsilon = 0.996078$ kJ/mol and atomic mass $m = 39.948$ u. Although this package can be used for well-known continuous potentials, as for example: Lennard-Jones, Coulomb and Buckingham potentials, it also can be used for other type of interactions that can be presented in an input table with a very fine discretization. We have done this for the CSW potential with an spacing gap of 0.00001 nm to reproduce the continuous force minimum. In contrast to the SW potential that has a fixed range, for the CSW potential it is necessary to define a cut-off distance. In GROMACS distance units, it was chosen at the distance for which the potential has an approximated value $U_{CSW}(r_c) \approx 10^{-15}$ kJ/mol. For instance, for a CSW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$ the cut-off is $r = 0.512$ nm (approximately 1.504σ) with $n = 2500$ and $m = 20000$. This criterion for defining the CSW range slightly overestimates the corresponding SW range. We will refer to a CSW potential of a given range λ that corresponds to the SW range that we want to mimic, although the CSW has

a slightly greater range. We included in the Appendix the program in Fortran that can make the Gromacs input file *table_Ar_Ar.xvg*.

In all NVT the leap-frog integrator algorithm [84], Nosé-Hoover thermostat [85] with a coupling constant $\tau = 2$ ps was used and a time step $\delta t = 0.0001$ ps. In Appendix B we give a brief analysis of the time step selection accordingly to the n and m values.

Periodic boundary conditions in all directions and neighbour list to speed up calculation were implemented.

To compare with available simulation data, our results will be presented in the following reduced units: density $\rho^* = \rho\sigma^3$, temperature $T^* = k_B T/\epsilon$, excess internal energy $u = U/NkT$, reduced pressure is $P^* = P\sigma^3/\epsilon$, and compressibility factor $Z = P^*/\rho^*T^*$.

Supercritical state properties were calculated from NVT simulations with a starting crystalline array conformed by 1000 particles. To equilibrate the system $2 * 10^6$ time steps were used and to take averages $2 * 10^7$ steps divided in ten sub-blocks.

To calculate the vapor-liquid coexistence we have carried out NVT simulations in a parallelepiped simulation box with $L_z > L_x = L_y$ [86, 87]. We started with a cubic crystalline array with 2000 particles at a reduced density $\rho^* = 0.8$, the liquid state at the desired temperature has been reached after 10^6 steps.

Subsequently, L_z was elongated with the ratio $L_z/L_x = 4$ where $L_x \approx 13.57\sigma$ and a second simulation was performed with $4 * 10^7$ steps in order to allow the phase separation. The coexistence densities were obtained from the density profiles $\rho(z) = \langle N(z) \rangle / \delta V$, where $\langle N(z) \rangle$ is the average number of molecules within a slab of volume δV calculated every 10000 steps in each slab of volume $\delta V = L_x * L_y * (L_z/500)$.

Extended simulations were employed ($2 * 10^8$ steps) to determine the surface tension and results were computed via the components of the pressure tensor.

$$\gamma^* = \frac{L_z^*}{2} \left[\langle P_{zz}^* \rangle - \frac{1}{2} (\langle P_{xx}^* \rangle + \langle P_{yy}^* \rangle) \right], \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma^* = \gamma\sigma^2/\epsilon$ is the reduced surface tension, $L_z^* = L_z/\sigma$, $\langle P_{xx}^* \rangle$, $\langle P_{yy}^* \rangle$ and $\langle P_{zz}^* \rangle$ are the average components of the pressure tensor in the x , y and z directions, respectively.

4 Results

4.1 Single state properties

We will test the performance of the CSW against SW available simulation data.

As a first test of the CSW potential we have carried out single state NVT simulations for the most famous case studied in the context of simple fluids, $\lambda = 1.5$, at supercritical states (SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$ has a reduced critical temperature value around 1.22 [36, 38, 40, 41]). In Figure 2 CSW potential reduced internal energies and compressibility factors as a function of temperature, $u(T^*)$ and $Z(T^*)$, for $\rho^* = 0.8$ are presented. As can be seen the CSW predictions are in good agreement with reported SW simulation data by Labík et al. [39].

For colloids models it is also important to consider cases of shorter ranges [24, 88, 89], so we also compared the reduced excess internal energy for a CSW potential of range $\lambda = 1.25$, at $\rho^* = 0.6$ for several super critical temperatures (the critical temperature $T_c^* \approx 0.76$ [36, 41]) and are presented in Figure 3. Although the Patel et al. [47] reported values have large errors (not shown in this figure), our simulation data are in agreement with their central values.

In order to compare the structural properties of CSW and SW potentials we have calculated the radial distribution function $g(r^*)$. As can be seen in Figure 4 the CSW potential reproduces the structural behavior of an equivalent SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$ at $T^* = 2.0$ and $\rho^* = 0.8$, reported by Henderson et al. [33], including the contact values.

To test the performance of this CSW potential in the fcc solid phase we present in Table 1 a comparison of the internal energy and pressure predicted for a SW of range $\lambda = 1.5$ by Young and Alder [90]. As can be seen the agreement of the pressures is quite reasonable well, considering that in MC simulation the pressures are indirectly obtained through extrapolations of the contact values of the radial distribution functions. For the internal energies, the agreement is very good. The errors on the internal energies and pressures were estimated by

4.2 Vapor-Liquid Coexistence

NVT simulations were carried out to compute the liquid-vapor coexistence densities for several temperatures, for a system of particles interacting with the CSW potential Eq. (2) with ranges $\lambda = 1.25, 1.5, 1.75$. In Table 2 the simulation data for liquid and vapor coexistence densities are presented.

The orthobaric densities were obtained from the density profiles along the z^* axis and in Figure 5 the distribution is shown for a CSW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$ for temperatures in the interval $[0.8, 1.15]$. The highest temperature was simulated with 5000 particle, instead of 2000, to have a liquid slab of similar size. In Figure 6 a good agreement with previous simulation data for the vapor and liquid coexistence densities from different authors and different simulation techniques can be noticed.

The vapor-liquid coexistence for a CSW potential of ranges $\lambda = 1.25$ and $\lambda = 1.75$ are shown in Figure 7 and 8, respectively. The agreement of the simulation data obtained in this work and available simulation data of other authors is good for the states presented.

Reduced Vapor pressure were computed using the zz -component of the tensor pressure, $P_v^* = P_{zz}^*$, for CSW $\lambda = 1.5$. As can be noticed from Figure 9 the simulated pressures are in agreement with MC data from Orea et al. [43] and Singh et al.[44]. The simulation vapor pressures are included in Table 2. The standard deviations were obtained, after the first 0.5 ns, by using the averages of 10 sub-blocks of 0.35 ns each one.

Lastly, we have carried out longer simulations of 20 ns to compute the surface tension of a CSW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$. This property was obtained, as mentioned in the simulation details section, from the pressure components Eq. (4) which were averaged every 4 ns. The final mean surface tension are presented in Table 2, plotted in Figure 10 and contrasted with previous results for a SW fluid. As can be seen the predictions are in a good agreement with the available simulation data.

It is important to remark that although this CSW potential reproduces quantitatively well the discontinuous SW potential properties it is restricted to the use of low time steps values (0.0001 ps of range $\lambda = 1.5$) that result in long time MD simulation runs.

However, there could be also interest in using this continuous potential expression using lower exponent values, like for instance, the ones shown in Fig 1, (400, 400), that also captures the essential characteristics of the SW potential and can be studied using a time step one order of magnitude greater (see Appendix B).

5 Corollary

As a consequence of this work we found the following Continuous Version of the Square-Shoulder (CSS) potential that, as mentioned in the introduction, it is also a very interesting simple discrete potential that exhibits a rich phase behavior that can model real simple and complex systems [28]. The CSS potential can be written as:

$$u_{CSS}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{1}{x} \right)^n - \frac{1 - e^{-m(x-a)(x-\lambda)}}{1 + e^{-m(x-a)(x-\lambda)}} + 1 \right), \quad (5)$$

where $a = 0.99$. A plot of this potential can be found in Figure 11 where the discrete version is compared to the continuous version. The exploration of the phase diagram for this potential will be of interest in future studies.

6 Conclusions

We have presented a simple continuous mathematical expression for the discontinuous square-well potential of variable range ($\lambda \geq 1.05$). Molecular Dynamics simulations were used with this potential and its predictions were compared with available simulation data (single state thermodynamic properties (gas, liquid and solid), vapor-liquid phase diagram and surface tension) and its performance was good. We expect that this continuous version of the square-well potential can be useful to overcome the difficulties of treating discontinuous potentials in statistical mechanics problems, as for example in conventional Molecular Dynamics simulations.

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References

- [1] F. del Río and L. Lira, *Mol. Phys.* **61**, 275 (1987).
- [2] F. del Río and L. Lira, *J. Chem. Phys.* **87**, 7179 (1987).
- [3] A. L. Benavides and F. del Río, *Mol. Phys.* **68**, 983 (1989).
- [4] A. L. Benavides and A. Gil-Villegas, *Mol. Phys.* **97**, 1225 (1999).
- [5] J. Chang and S. I. Sandler, *Mol. Phys.* **81**, 745 (1994).
- [6] A. Vidales, A. L. Benavides, and A. Gil-Villegas, *Mol. Phys.* **99**, 703 (2001).
- [7] G. A. Chapela, F. del Río, A. L. Benavides, and J. Alejandre, *J. Chem. Phys.* **133**, 234107 (2010).
- [8] L. A. Cervantes, G. Jaime-Muñoz, A. L. Benavides, J. Torres-Arenas, and F. Sastre, *J. Chem. Phys.* **142**, 114501 (2015).
- [9] I. M. Zerón, L. A. Padilla, F. Gámez, J. Torres-Arenas, and A. L. Benavides, *J. Mol. Liq.* **229**, 125 (2017).
- [10] A. Gil-Villegas, A. Galindo, P. J. Whitehead, S. J. Mills, G. Jackson, and A. N. Burgess, *J. Chem. Phys.* **106**, 4168 (1997).
- [11] A. Galindo, L. A. Davies, A. Gil-Villegas, and G. Jackson, *Mol. Phys.* **93**, 241 (1998).
- [12] E. B. El Mendoub , J.-F. Wax , I. Charpentier, and N. Jakse, *Mol. Phys.* **106**, 20 (2008).
- [13] F. J. Martínez-Ruiz, F. J. Blas, A. I. Moreno-Ventas Bravo, J. M. Míguez, and L. G. MacDowell, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **19**, 12296 (2017).
- [14] K. B. Hollingshead and T. M. Truskett, *Phys. Rev. E* **91**, 043307 (2015).
- [15] S. P. Hlushak, P. A. Hlushak, and A. Trokhymchuk, *J. Chem. Phys.* **138**, 164107 (2013).
- [16] C. Thomson, L. Lue, and M. N. Bannerman, *J. Chem. Phys.* **140**, 034105 (2014).
- [17] M. G. Noro, D. Frenkel, *J. Chem. Phys.* **113**, 2941 (2000).
- [18] A. Gil-Villegas, C. Vega, F. Del Río and A. Malijevsky, *Mol. Phys.* **86**, 857 (1995).
- [19] D. Fiocco, G. Pastore, and G. Foffi, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **114** , 12085 (2010).
- [20] M. A. Miller and D. Frenkel, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **16**, S4901 (2004).
- [21] N. Kern, D. Frenkel, *J. Chem. Phys.* **118**, 9882 (2003).
- [22] P. G. Bolhuis, A. Stroobants, D. Frenkel, and H. N. W. Lekkerkerker, *J. Chem. Phys.* **107**, 1551 (1997).
- [23] P. R. ten Wolde and D. Frenkel, *Science* **277**, 1975 (1997).

- [24] N. E. Valadez Pérez, A. L. Benavides, E. Schöll-Paschinger, and R. Castañeda-Priego, *J. Chem. Phys.* **137**, 084905 (2012).
- [25] G. Foffi, G. D. McCullagh, A. Lawlor, E. Zaccarelli, K. A. Dawson, F. Sciortino, P. Tartaglia, D. Pini, and G. Stell, *Phys. Rev. E* **65**, 031407 (2002).
- [26] G. J. Pauschenweina and G. Kahl, *Soft Matter* **4**, 1396 (2008).
- [27] P. Bolhuis and D. Frenkel, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **9**, 381 (1997).
- [28] H. Pattabhiraman, G. Avvisati, and M. Dijkstra *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **119**, 157401 (2017).
- [29] G. Malescio and G. Pellicane *Nature Materials* **2**, 97 (2003).
- [30] G. Malescio and G. Pellicane *Phys. Rev. E* **70**, 021202 (2004).
- [31] J. Fornleitner and G. Kahl, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **22**,104118 (2010).
- [32] J. C. Armas-Pérez, J. Quintana, G. A. Chapela, E. Velasco, and G. Navascués, *J. Chem. Phys.* **140**, 064503 (2014).
- [33] D. Henderson, W. G. Madden, and D. D. Fitts, *J. Chem. Phys.* **64**, 5026 (1976).
- [34] D. Henderson, O. H. Scalise, and W. R. Smith, *J. Chem. Phys.* **72**, 2431 (1980).
- [35] D. M. Heyes and P. J. Aston, *J. Chem. Phys.* **97**, 5738 (1992).
- [36] L. Vega, E. de Miguel, L. F. Rull, G. Jackson, and I. A. McLure, *J. Chem. Phys.* **96**, 2296 (1992).
- [37] E. de Miguel, *Phys. Rev. E* **55**, 1347 (1997).
- [38] J. R. Elliott and L. Hu, *J. Chem. Phys.* **110**, 3043 (1999).
- [39] S. Labík, A. Malijevský, R. Kao, W. R. Smith, and F. Del Río, *Mol. Phys.* **96**, 849 (1999).
- [40] G. Orkoulas and A. Z. Panagiotopoulos, *J. Chem. Phys.* **110**, 1581 (1999).
- [41] F. Del Río, E. Ávalos , R. Espíndola , L. F. Rull , G. Jackson, and S. Lago, *Mol. Phys.* **100**, 2531 (2002).
- [42] S. B. Kiselev, J. F. Ely, L. Lue, and J. R. Elliott, *Fluid Phase Equilibr.* **200**, 121 (2002).
- [43] P. Orea, Y. Duda, and José Alejandro, *J. Chem. Phys.* **118**, 5635 (2003).
- [44] J. K. Singh, D. A. Kofke, and J. R. Errington, *J. Chem. Phys.* **119**, 3405 (2003).
- [45] P. Orea, Y. Duda, V. C. Weiss, W. Schröer, and J. Alejandro, *J. Chem. Phys.* **120**, 11754 (2004).

- [46] G. J. Gloor, G. Jackson, F. J. Blas, and E. de Miguel, *J. Chem. Phys.* **123**, 134703 (2005).
- [47] B. H. Patel, H. Docherty, S. Varga, A. Galindo, and G. C. Maitland, *Mol. Phys.* **103**, 129 (2005).
- [48] D. L. Pagan and J. D. Gunton, *J. Chem. Phys.* **122**, 184515 (2005).
- [49] R. López-Rendón, Y. Reyes, and P. Orea, *J. Chem. Phys.* **125**, 084508 (2006).
- [50] R. Espíndola-Heredia, F. del Río, and A. Malijevsky, *J. Chem. Phys.* **130**, 024509 (2009).
- [51] Y. T. Pavlyukhin, *J. Struct. Chem.* **53**, 476 (2012).
- [52] J. Jover, A. J. Haslam, A. Galindo, G. Jackson, and E. A. Müller, *J. Chem. Phys.* **137**, 144505 (2012).
- [53] H. Neitsch and S. H. L. Klapp, *J. Chem. Phys.* **138**, 064904 (2013).
- [54] J. R. Solana, *J. Chem. Phys.* **129**, 244502 (2009).
- [55] H. J. C. Berendsen, D. van der Spoel, and R. van Drunen, *Comp. Phys. Comm.* **91**, 43 (1995).
- [56] E. Lindahl, B. Hess and D. van der Spoel, *J. Mol. Model.* **7**, 306 (2001).
- [57] D. van der Spoel, E. Lindahl, B. Hess, G. Groenhof, A. E. Mark, and H. J. C. Berendsen, *J. Comput. Chem.* **26**, 1701 (2005).
- [58] B. Hess, C. Kutzner, D. van der Spoel, and E. Lindahl, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **4**, 435 (2008).
- [59] S. Pronk, S. Páll, R. Schulz, P. Larsson, P. Bjelkmar, R. Apostolov, M. R. Shirts, J. C. Smith, P. M. Kasson, D. van der Spoel, B. Hess, and E. Lindahl, *Bioinformatics* **29**, 845 (2013).
- [60] S. Páll, M. J. Abraham, C. Kutzner, B. Hess, and E. Lindahl, *Proc. of EASC 2015 LNCS*, 8759 3 (2015).
- [61] M. J. Abraham, T. Murtola, R. Schulz, S. Páll, J. C. Smith, B. Hess, and E. Lindahl, *SoftwareX* **1**, 19 (2015).
- [62] B. R. Brooks, C. L. Brooks, A. D. Mackerell, L. Nilsson, R. J. Petrella, B. Roux, Y. Won, G. Archontis, C. Bartels, S. Boresch, A. Caffisch, L. Caves, Q. Cui, A. R. Dinner, M. Feig, S. Fischer, J. Gao, M. Hodoscek, W. Im, K. Kuczera, T. Lazaridis, J. Ma, V. Ovchinnikov, E. Paci, R. W. Pastor, C. B. Post, J. Z. Pu, M. Schaefer, B. Tidor, R. M. Venable, H. L. Woodcock, X. Wu, W. Yang, D. M. York, and M. Karplus, *J. Comp. Chem.* **30**, 1545 (2009).
- [63] I. T. Todorov, W. Smith, K. Trachenko, and M. T. Dove, *J. Mater. Chem.* **16**, 1911 (2006).

- [64] H. J. Limbach, A. Arnold, B. A. Mann, and C. Holm, *Comp. Phys. Comm.* **174**, 704 (2006).
- [65] J. Roth, F. Gähler, and H.R. Trebin, *Int. J. Mod. Phys. C* **11**, 317 (2000).
- [66] S. Plimpton, *J. Comp. Phys.* **117**, 1 (1995).
- [67] C. Niethammer, S. Becker, M. Bernreuther, M. Buchholz, W. Eckhardt, A. Heinecke, S. Werth, H.-J. Bungartz, C. W. Glass, H. Hasse, J. Vrabc, and M. Horsch, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **10**, 4455 (2014).
- [68] J. C. Phillips, R. Braun, W. Wang, J. Gumbart, E. Tajkhorshid, E. Villa, C. Chipot, R. D. Skeel, L. Kale, and K. Schulten, *J. Comp. Chem.* **26**, 1781 (2005).
- [69] P. Ren and J. W. Ponder, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **107**, 5933 (2003).
- [70] J. A. Anderson, C. D. Lorentz, and A. Travesst, *J. Comput. Phys.* **227**, 10 (2008)
- [71] J. Glaser, T. D. Nguyen, J. A. Anderson, P. Liu, F. Spiga, J. A. Millan, D. C. Morse, and S. C. Glotzer, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 192 (2015).
- [72] B. J. Alder and T. E. Wainwright, *J. Chem. Phys.* **31**, 459 (1959).
- [73] G. A. Chapela, S. E. Martínez-Casas, and J. Alejandre, *Mol. Phys.* **53**, 139 (1984).
- [74] J. C. Armas-Pérez, J. Quintana-H, and G. A. Chapela, *J. Chem. Phys.* **138**, 044508 (2013).
- [75] J. Cui and J. R. Elliott, *J. Chem. Phys.* **116**, 8625 (2002).
- [76] M. N. Bannerman, R. Sargant, and L. Lue, *J. Comput. Chem.* **32**, 3329 (2011).
- [77] P. Orea and G. Odriozola, *J. Chem. Phys.* **138**, 214105 (2013).
- [78] L. A. Padilla and A. L. Benavides, *J. of Chem. Phys.* **147**, 034502 (2017).
- [79] J. R. Espinosa, E. Sanz, C. Valeriani and C. Vega, *J. Chem. Phys.* **139**, 144502 (2013).
- [80] Y. D. Fomin, N. V. Gribova, V. N. Ryzhov, S. M. Stishov, and D. Frenkel, *J. Chem. Phys.* **129**, 064512 (2008).
- [81] N. V. Gribova, Y. D. Fomin, D. Frenkel, and V. N. Ryzhov, *Phys. Rev. E* **79**, 051202 (2009).
- [82] G. Franzese, *J. Mol. Liq.* **136**, 267 (2007).
- [83] J. Y. Abraham, S. V. Buldyrev, and N. Giovambattista, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **115**, 14229 (2011).
- [84] D. Beeman, *J. Comput. Phys.* **20**, 130 (1976).
- [85] S. Nosé, *J. Chem. Phys.* **81**, 515 (1984).

- [86] G. A. Chape, G. Saville, and J. S. Rowlinson, *Faraday Discuss. Chem. Soc.* **59**, 22 (1975).
- [87] G. A. Chapela, G. Saville, S. M. Thompson, and J. S. Rowlinson, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2* **73**, 1133 (1977).
- [88] Y. Duda, *J. Chem. Phys.* **130**, 116101 (2009).
- [89] L. Acedo and A. Santos, *J. Chem. Phys.* **115**, 2805 (2001).
- [90] D. A. Young and B. J. Alder, *J. Chem. Phys.* **73**, 2430 (1980).
- [91] J. R. Errington, *J. Chem. Phys.* **118**, 9915 (2003).

A Fortran program for the tabulated CSW potential for GROMACS 5.1

This program generates the Gromacs input file '*table_Ar_Ar.xvg*', in which the potential CSW and its force have been tabulated.

The LJ parameters for Argon are the diameter in nanometers and the energy minimum ϵ in kJ/mol.

```
program (tabulation CSW)

implicit double precision(a-h,o-z)

dimension u(1000000), rr(1000000), deri(1000000), fuerza(1000000)

open(unit=3,file="table_Ar_Ar.xvg", &status = "unknown")

sigma = 0.3405d0

xepsilon = 0.996078d0

cero=0.d0

c These are the CSW parameters.
c xlam is the range of the SW potential that we wish to mimic.

xlam = 1.5d0

c This is the exponent that characterizes the softness of the repulsive part
of the CSW.

n = 2500

c This is the exponent that characterizes the softness of the attractive part of
the CSW potential.

m = 20000

c Since it is not necessary to evaluate the potential from  $r = 0$  we start
at  $r = 0.2$ 

overlap = 0.2d0

c The spacing gap in the table.

c The potential will be evaluated every 0.00001, starting at  $r = 0.2$ .

dis = 0.00001d0

c This is the table cutoff reported in the grompp.mdp file in Gromacs see
```

'User-specified potential functions' from the Gromacas manual.

```
nsteps=0.850d0/dis
```

```
xn = nsteps
```

```
nsteps=nint(xn)
```

```
do ir=1,nsteps+3
```

```
c The number 3 is added to have at least data from  $r = 0$  to  $r=table$  cut-off.
```

```
rr(ir)=0.0d0 + (ir-1.d0)*dis
```

```
if (rr(ir).lt.overlap) then
```

```
u(ir)=0.00d0
```

```
deri(ir)=0.0d0
```

```
fuerza(ir) = -deri(ir)
```

```
write(3,200) rr(ir),cero,cero,u(ir),fuerza(ir),cero,cero
```

```
else
```

```
x = rr(ir)/sigma
```

```
c Here we start to build the mathematical expression for the CSW potential and its force
```

```
arg= -m * (x - xlam) * (x - 1.d0)
```

```
if(arg.ge.600.d0) then
```

```
c To avoid computational limits in evaluating big numbers, we have limited the exponential argument. Bigger than this number can generate errors
```

```
arg= 600.d0
```

```
endif
```

```
c This is the CSW potential
```

```
u(ir) = xepsilon*0.5d0*((1.d0/x)**n+(1.d0-dexp(arg))/(1.d0+dexp(arg))-1.d0)
```

```
c This is the CSW force
```

```
deri(ir) = xepsilon * 0.5d0 * (1.d0/sigma) * (-n * (1.d0/x) ** (n + 1.d0) + 2.d0 *
```

```

m*(2.d0*x - xlam - 1.d0)*dexp(arg)/((1.d0+dexp(arg))*(1.d0+dexp(arg)))

fuerza(ir) = - deri(ir)

if (x.gt.xlam) then

c We selected a criterium to set the rcut of the CSW potential and its force
when they differ to zero in 10-16

if(-u(ir).le.1.d-16) then

u(ir) = cero

endif

if(deri(ir).le.1.d-16) then

fuerza(ir) = cero

endif

endif

c These are restrictions of Gromacs 5.1 to handle very small and very big
numbers so we fixed the potential and the force to zero for such cases.

if(u(ir).ge.1.d30) then

u(ir) = cero

fuerza(ir) = -cero

endif

if(Abs(fuerza(ir)).lt.1.d-99) then

fuerza(ir) = cero

endif

write(3,200) rr(ir),cero,cero,u(ir),fuerza(ir),cero,cero

endif

enddo

200 format(2x,7(E15.8,4x))

stop
end

```

A Time-step and (n, m) optimized selection

The CSW potential depends on n and m parameters (see Figure 12) and these values are related to the steepness around σ and λ of the mimicked SW potential. In Molecular Dynamics simulations small time steps are required for potentials that are very steep. We performed NVT MD simulations using 1000 particles at a density $\rho^* = 0.8$ and $T^* = 2$. We analyzed different (n, m) parameter sets and to prevent that the simulation crashes due to particle overlapping we needed to test different time steps and we found for the (n, m) cases considered in this work the time-step upper limits reported in Table 3.

Notice that one needs to decrease one order of magnitude the time step in going from $(600, 600)$ to $(1500, 20000)$ cases. Doing a more fine time-step search for the case selected in this work $(2500, 20000)$ we found that we could use $\delta t = 0.0003$ but we decided to use $\delta t = 0.0001$ to guarantee not having problems in any of the CSW different sates of matter studied.

The selection of the set $(2500, 20000)$ used in this work has been done by analyzing the performance of the CSW potential that best mimicked the SW ($\lambda = 1.5$) potential. We selected some target properties: single state properties (internal energies, pressures, and pair correlation functions) and vapor-liquid coexistence densities.

We found that if we want to reproduce accurately the SW potential properties, these $(2500, 20000)$ high values are required. See for example Figure 13 that shows the simulated SW pair correlation function obtained by Henderson et al. [33] and different CSW potentials. As can be noticed if one wants to accurately reproduce the first pair correlation peak we need to use around $(2500, 20000)$ values.

Nevertheless, if one is interested in only qualitatively describing a SW behavior one can try smaller n and m values (around $(600, 600)$) and then use a one order of magnitude greater time step as can be seen in Table 3.

Besides, in Figure 14 the internal energy $U/N\epsilon$ for the same thermodynamic state is shown for several CSW cases and the simulation data of Labík et al. [39]. Again the best CSW performance is obtained with the case $(2500, 20000)$.

We did a similar analysis with other properties and found that the CSW potential with $(2500, 20000)$ showed the best performance when compared with available SW simulation data.

Table 1: Comparison of the SW and CSW solid (fcc structure) thermodynamic properties: reduced internal energy, $U/N\epsilon$, and pressure, P^* , for the range $\lambda = 1.5$ at temperatures $T^* = 0.7, 1.0$, and 1.2 and density $\rho^* = 1.285649$. The SW results are from Young and Alder [90].

Potential	T^*	P^*	$U/N\epsilon$
SW	0.7	18.55	-8.95
CSW	0.7	18.82(8)	-8.93(1)
SW	1.0	29.47	-8.92
CSW	1.0	29.61(11)	-8.89(1)
SW	1.2	68.65	-8.87
CSW	1.2	68.17(14)	-8.79(1)

Table 2: Vapor-liquid coexistence properties for a CSW potential of range $\lambda = 1.25, 1.5$ and 1.75 . Numbers in parentheses indicate the standard deviation of the properties in the last two digits.

T^*	ρ_v^*	ρ_l^*	P_v^*	γ^*
$\lambda = 1.25$				
0.62	0.0239(09)	0.8597(54)	0.0137(14)	
0.64	0.0310(11)	0.8387(69)	0.0173(11)	
0.66	0.0391(14)	0.8213(61)	0.0219(17)	
0.70	0.0696(18)	0.7567(43)	0.0355(19)	
$\lambda = 1.5$				
0.80	0.0057(05)	0.7310(39)	0.0040(16)	0.58(5)
0.85	0.0092(05)	0.7130(39)	0.0070(15)	0.49(4)
0.8774	0.0120(06)	0.7011(29)	0.0097(21)	0.45(5)
0.90	0.0144(07)	0.6932(38)	0.0106(21)	0.42(3)
0.95	0.0217(07)	0.6713(38)	0.0156(24)	0.35(4)
1.00	0.0292(08)	0.6477(34)	0.0242(21)	0.27(4)
1.05	0.0438(12)	0.6182(33)	0.0351(25)	0.20(4)
1.10	0.0618(20)	0.5828(35)	0.0478(18)	0.14(3)
1.15	0.0917(23)	0.5342(27)	0.0646(12)	0.07(4)
$\lambda = 1.75$				
1.20	0.0084(04)	0.6649(37)	0.0090(35)	
1.40	0.0245(08)	0.5928(38)	0.0283(31)	
1.60	0.0582(13)	0.5083(34)	0.0628(32)	

Table 3: Recommended maximum time step to be used with CSW (n, m) potentials to avoid simulation crashes.

CSW Potential	Maximum time step
(100, 100)	0.006
(200, 200)	0.003
(300, 300)	0.002
(400, 400)	0.001
(600, 600)	0.001
(1500, 20000)	0.0003
(2500, 20000)	0.0003

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

1. CSW and SW potentials for the case of SW range $\lambda = 1.5$. In the top panel the potentials are shown and in the bottom panel their corresponding forces as a function of the interparticle distance x . In this figure we have used $n = 400$ and $m = 400$ to amplify the softness of the CSW potential since for the exponent values used in this work ($n = 2500$ and $m = 20000$) the CSW and SW potentials are almost identical in the scale of the plot.
2. Supercritical excess internal energy, U/NkT , (top) and compressibility factor, Z , (bottom) as a function of reduced temperature for the CSW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$ at a reduced density $\rho^* = 0.8$. Results of this work are shown with red circles and with blue triangles the SW Monte Carlo simulation data from Labík et. al. [39].
3. Internal energies for a CSW potential of range $\lambda = 1.25$ at $\rho^* = 0.6$ for several super critical temperatures obtained in this work (red circles). Simulation central data (blue squares) from Patel et al. [47] are also included. Our simulation error bars are smaller than the symbol size used.
4. CSW potential radial distribution function for the case $\lambda = 1.5$ at temperature $T^* = 2.0$ and reduced density $\rho^* = 0.8$. Continuous line are predictions from this work and blue filled diamonds are SW MC results from Henderson et al. [33].
5. Density profiles for the CSW for $\lambda = 1.5$.
6. Vapor-liquid phase diagram for a SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$. CSW results (red circles) and SW simulation data from Elliot and Hu [38] (black squares), Del Río et al. [41] (blue diamonds), Singh et al. [44] (brown triangle up), Orea et al. [43] (magenta triangles down), and Errington [91] (green triangles left) are presented. Error bars are smaller than symbol sizes.
7. Vapor-liquid phase diagram for a SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.25$ as obtained in this work (red circles) and simulation data from Elliot and Hu [38] (black squares), Del Río et al. [41] (blue diamonds), and López et al. [49] (green triangles). Error bars are smaller than symbol sizes.
8. Vapor-liquid coexistence for a SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.75$. Red circles symbols correspond to CSW potential and simulation data from Elliot and Hu [38] (black squares), Del Río et al. [41] (blue diamonds), and Singh et al. [44] (brown triangles up) are as well shown. Error bars are smaller than symbol sizes.
9. Reduced vapor pressures for a SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$. Simulation predictions for the CSW potential are shown (red circles). Data for the SW potential from Orea et al. [43] (blue squares) and Singh et al. [44] (brown triangles up) are shown.
10. Surface tension for a SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$. The corresponding CSW potential results are shown with red circles. SW simulation data from Orea et al. [43] (brown squares), Singh et al. [44] (blue triangles), and Gloor et al. [46] (green diamonds) are included.

11. CSS and SS potentials for the case of SS range $\lambda = 1.5$. In this figure we have used $n = 400$, $m = 400$ and $a = 0.9$ to amplify the softness of the CSS potential.
12. CSW (n, m) and SW potentials for the case $\lambda = 1.5$. The cases $(1500, 20000)$ and $(2500, 20000)$ overlap in this plot with the SW potential.
13. Radial distribution function for several CSW potential cases (n, m) at reduced density $\rho^* = 0.8$ and temperature $T^* = 2$. Simulation data for SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$ from Henderson et al.[33] are shown with diamond symbols.
14. Excess internal energy, $U/n\epsilon$, for several CSW potential (n, m) cases used to mimic the behavior of a SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5$ at reduced density $\rho^* = 0.8$ and temperature $T^* = 2$. Target simulation data from Labík et al.[39] is shown with a triangle symbol.